

Quantum Theory for Specific Case Study

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Abstract—In general, Quantum Computing works by computing logical operators as quantum gates for secure communication of any preferred data within desired states and this data is transmitted in the form of Qubits. In Quantum Mechanics, we usually concerned about super position or entanglement of particle and it quantifies depth of entanglement based on number of Qubits within Coherence Time but in quantum computing, we deal with superposition of states i.e, $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ for secure communication of desired data moreover, methodology as Qiskit that works on logical operators and for computing it we need to build the system execute it.

Index Terms—Fourier Analysis, Logical Operators, Optimization, Quantum Mechanics and Quantum computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

In general, building the system to acquire desired output after execution depends on proper methodology and in quantum computing, Qiskit if preferable to build a system where quantum gates are predefined for desired states.

II. OPTIMIZATION BASED ON FOURIER TRANSFORMATION FOR QUANTUM COMPUTING

According to my understanding Computational analysis within Eigen States by logical operators or gates i.e, OR, XOR, NOT.. for instance mathematical optimization of fourier transformation based on eigen values within respective matrices is quantified in assumption of wave function, because Logical operators, specifically at eigen states performs outstandingly well for imaginary data since superposition of desired states **shifts** real data into **imaginary** during transmission of data within secure communication.

III. EIGEN STATES AND QUANTUM NETWORKS: A CASE STUDY

Dmitri Babikov et al [1] stated that he developed a system to study properties of quantum computing that uses vibrational eigen states but in my findings i understood that quantum computing and mechanics are two different aspects but can be related if one is dealing with quantum neural networks because superposition of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states for secure communication of data transmission will eventually leads to eigen states within quantum networks when super position triggers entanglement of molecule for certain pulses according to author et al [1].

IV. CONCLUSION

We finally conclude that in quantum computing, superposition of desired states shifts properties of real data into imaginary and as we mentioned in above section, i.e, superposition eventually leads to entanglement because of imaginary data.

REFERENCES

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